

22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport”

A1.2.1

Parameters that influence parallel sampling at HD-HRS and parameters that will be used in A1.2.3-A1.2.4

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Table of Contents

<u>1. Introduction</u>	4
<u>2. Parallel sampling parameters to be tested in A1.2.3 and A1.2.4</u>	5
<u>2.1 ZBT HD-HRS (for A1.2.3)</u>	5
<u>2.1.1 Fueling protocol</u>	5
<u>2.1.2 Parameters independent of the fueling protocol (Storage bank)</u>	6
<u>2.1.3 Safety considerations</u>	6
<u>2.2 Other possible sites to perform tests</u>	6

1. Introduction

The report A1.1.1 discussed the current and future specifications and operations of HD-HRS. Table 1 from this report which summarizes the operational parameters of HD-HRS for different supply options is reproduced below.

Table 1 - Operational parameters of HD-HRS for different supply options

Supply option	CGH ₂ , LH ₂	CGH ₂ , LH ₂	LH ₂	LH ₂ (CGH ₂ feasible)
HRS specifications				
Main components	H ₂ storage, compressor or cryo pump, cooling unit (if CGH ₂), dispenser (nozzle, hose)	H ₂ storage, compressor or cryo pump, cooling unit (if CGH ₂), dispenser (nozzle, hose)	H ₂ storage, subcooled liquid H ₂ pump, dispenser (nozzle, hose)	LH ₂ storage, cryo pump, dispenser (nozzle, hose)
H ₂ storage type	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage, pipeline	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage	Depending on specification either: trailer swap, supply storage
Refuelling pressure	350 bar	700 bar	Approx. 16 bar	300 bar
Ease of expanding to 700 bar passenger vehicles refuelling	Complex and costly integration due to higher compressor ratio and cooling demand	Relatively simple expandability due to existing technology and lower performance requirements	Complex and costly integration of additional high pressure cryo pump system, nozzle, hose etc	Complex and costly integration of additional high pressure cryo pump system, nozzle, hose etc
Data communication between HRS and vehicle	Necessary for better performance	Necessary for better performance	Not required	Not required
Targeted max flow rate	300 g/s	300 g/s	110-140 g/s (per pump)	55-220 g/s per pump
Vehicle specifications				
H ₂ tank pressure (MAWP*)	350 (437.5 bar)	700 (875 bar)	Approx. 5-16 bar	200-800 kg/h per pump
VH ₂ tank temperature	-40 to 85 °C	-40 to 85 °C	-248 to -245 °C	Approx. -240 °C to -150 °C
Storage capacity	Today <42.5 kg (intended > 42.5 kg)	Up to 100 kg	>80 kg	> 80 kg

Two main hydrogen fuel sampling strategies are currently used at light-duty hydrogen refuelling stations: parallel sampling or direct sampling. The strategies are being adapted to heavy-duty conditions.

This document focuses on parallel sampling and heavy-duty refuelling stations.

Parallel sampling involves taking a hydrogen sample during a HD-FCEV refill, which is undertaken using a filling protocol that includes pressure ramp and flow variation. The impact of these parameters

is currently unknown, and it may significantly affect the integrity or representativeness of the sample taken.

A1.1.3 report summarizes the parameters and their expected impact on sampling (either gas composition or particulates). The following critical parameters that influence the quality control sampling of hydrogen were defined:

- Pressure
- Storage bank homogeneity
- Flowrate
- Temperature
- Safety considerations

The Table 2 below shows only the information related to parallel sampling.

Table 2. Summary of the parameters considered and expected impact (+: expected impact on the sampling parameter being either gas composition or particulate amount fraction).

Sampling	Pressure	Temperature	Flow rate	Storage bank	Safety	Additional
Gas composition	+ (fueling protocol)	+ (fueling protocol) (water impact)	+ (fueling protocol)	+ (fueling protocol)	+	Fueling protocol
Particulates	+ (fueling protocol)	+ (fueling protocol) (Water freezing)	+ (fueling protocol)	?	+	Fueling protocol

During a parallel sampling, the sample taken is following the fueling protocol therefore some parameters are determined by the protocol (start temperature, flow rate and pressure ramp) while other parameters like the storage bank are based on the availability of hydrogen in the different storages. In summary, the storage bank can affect the sampling realisation however the current sampling protocol are not selecting always the same condition (i.e., successive refuelling may use different amount of the storage bank available to optimise the refuelling).

For parallel sampling, the first approach will be to identify how the current fueling protocol and the parameters defined affect the sampling.

2. Parallel sampling parameters to be tested in A1.2.3 and A1.2.4

In the project, several HRS were identified based on their ability to control and vary parameters for parallel sampling. The following section will review the possibility at ZBT HD-HRS and at other sites identified

2.1 ZBT HD-HRS (for A1.2.3)

For the testing of fueling protocol impact on parallel sampling, there is some parameters that will be fixed and the ability to vary the fueling protocol.

2.1.1 Fueling protocol

2.1.1.1 *Dynamic parameters: pressure and flow*

For the samplings, it is possible to use refuelling protocols which specify pressure ramp rates like the protocol from CEP and Wenger Engineering (Minimum Ambient Precooling (MAP) Hydrogen Refuelling Protocol for 35MPa Heavy Duty Vehicles (20-42.5 kg)).

Alternatively, it is possible to operate a refuelling with the MC method (according to TIR SAE J2601-5).

Due to the layout of the testing platform at ZBT, the pressure losses in the pipes and the components limit the maximum flow through the nozzle in the CHSS. Consequently, there is a maximum pressure ramp rate in dependence of the volume of the CHSS.

The flowrate at the ZBT facility is restricted due to pressure losses in the pipes etc. In the current setup, the station can provide approximately a maximum flowrate of 70 g/s.

In 2025, the HRS setup at ZBT site will be extended within the frame of the RHeadHy project. The goal of this extension is to allow refuellings with very high flow (70 MPa, 300 g/s) at the testing platform.

2.1.1.2 *Fixed parameters: temperature of hydrogen fuel*

To take a sample with the heavy-duty equipment at the ZBT site, the fuel delivery temperature needs to be inside the temperature range of -20 to 20 °C as the WEH TK16 nozzle for 35 MPa refuellings is used (the minimum media temperature for this nozzle is -20 °C). In this range, the gas temperature can be defined with the refuelling protocols.

2.1.2 Parameters independent of the fueling protocol (Storage bank):

During a refuelling process, hydrogen from different storage banks is used to decrease temperature effects and to avoid efficiency losses through unnecessary gas compression to higher pressure levels. At the start, when the pressure in the CHSS is low, the hydrogen flows out of a pressure bank with a low pressure level. When the pressure differs between the storage bank and the CHSS and the flow decreases, a storage bank with a higher pressure is used.

This mechanism is not defined in the refuelling protocols and needs to be implemented in the HRS control. At ZBT site, it can be defined for every refuelling which storage banks should be used and which pressure difference is significant for the shift of the storage banks.

2.1.3 Safety considerations

Because of the lack of standardized protocols and not enough experience with high flow heavy-duty refuellings, it is advisable to use a CHSS with temperature sensors inside to track the gas temperature and to avoid exceeding the temperature limit of the tank.

2.1.3.1 *Venting*

The venting at the station is part of the automated refuelling process. The used sampling system has its own vent which is used to purge the system and to release the pressure after the refuelling. The vent can be operated with the usual procedure for sampling.

2.2 Other possible sites to perform tests

One additional site has been identified by CESAME: McPHY (French HRS manufacturer). McPHY has an R&D site where tests could be performed on HDV dispensers.

The HD-HRS parameters are compatible with the project objectives: flow up to 120 g/s, pressure of 35 MPa. Information on the ability to vary fueling protocol is under investigation as backup option. The flexibility of McPHY HRS is good and they can modify a lot of parameters on the station to fulfill our testing protocols. The maximum mass flow is currently limited to 120 g/s (expected to be extended up to 300 g/s next year).

Furthermore, the sampling and particulates testing is of great interest for McPHY which could be a strong collaborator for the consortium. The main challenge is the current global political organization as McPHY is selling its HRS activity to another company ATAWAY (French HRS manufacturer).

This organization's modification leads to challenges regarding the timing, the availability of the testing area or the staff. Therefore, the consortium considers this backup option as credible in 2025, if our first initial plan of performing testing at ZBT fails. Follow-up discussion with ATAWAY and MCPHY will be pursued during the project duration to ensure contingency is present.